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Optimizing photovoltaic-battery systems for net-billing in Greece: Impact of building usage and pricing schemes

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the techno-economic performance of photovoltaic–battery (PVB) systems under the Greek net-billing framework. A simulation-based optimization framework evaluates how building usage and electricity tariff structure influence system sizing, self-consumption, and profitability. Three building types (residential, retail, and office) are analyzed under flat, dual-zone time-of-use (ToU), and real-time pricing (RTP) schemes, complemented by sensitivity analyses on price levels and volatility. The RTP scheme is derived from hourly wholesale market data, capturing realistic price variability in the Greek context. Building usage is found to be the dominant factor shaping PVB behavior. Residential buildings achieve the highest self-consumption (40–60%) with balanced PV-to-battery ratios (≈ 4 kW/10 kWh), while retail buildings require larger systems (≈ 6 kW/16–18 kWh) to meet daytime loads. Offices exhibit the lowest performance (5–30%) due to limited operation. Transitioning from a flat to a ToU tariff increases self-consumption by up to 20 percentage points, whereas RTP further enlarges storage capacities (up to 18 kWh) but yields only marginal self-consumption gains. Across all cases, payback periods remain within 6–8 years, as capacities adapt to maintain profitability under different tariffs. Sensitivity analyses show that PV sizing depends mainly on feed-in remuneration, while storage investment is driven by import prices and price volatility. As volatility decreases, battery capacity and profitability decline, while PV sizing remains stable. Overall, moderate temporal differentiation, such as refined ToU tariffs aligned with typical demand profiles, offers a balanced pathway for net-billing prosumers, enhancing flexibility and economic performance without the operational complexity of full RTP.

1. Introduction

The urgency of mitigating climate change and fossil fuel depletion has elevated the transition to sustainable energy systems into a global priority. The building sector contributes significantly to the global energy crisis, as it currently accounts for approximately 30% of the global energy consumption and 37% of CO₂ emissions, primarily from building operations and material production [1].

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Targeting this sector therefore offers substantial potential for reducing both energy use and emissions. In line with these objectives, the European Union has committed to transforming its building stock into zero-emission buildings by 2050, as outlined in the EU Green Deal and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [2]. Key measures include enhancing energy efficiency, and critically, integrating renewable energy sources (RES), such as solar, wind, geothermal, for on-site energy generation [3].

Building envelopes offer potential spaces for installing RES, complemented by energy storage systems as batteries. This integration enables buildings to function as active energy nodes, promoting self-use energy generation and exporting surplus energy to the grid, thereby contributing to the global shift to renewable energy sources. One of the most favored and cost-effective options for on-site energy production is roof-mounted photovoltaic (PV) systems [4]. The installation of such systems has increased rapidly due to the technological maturity and the continuous decline in investment costs [5]. When combined with battery storage, these installations, referred to as photovoltaic-battery (PVB) systems, can effectively mitigate daily and seasonal variations in solar generation, thereby enhancing the reliability and self-sufficiency of the power supply [6]. To further incentivize adoption, legal and regulatory frameworks provide financial support in the form of subsidies, tax reductions, or compensation schemes such as feed-in-tariffs, net metering, and net billing [7]. These measures significantly improve the economic viability of PVB investments.

Net metering and net billing are two widely adopted electricity pricing remuneration schemes aimed at encouraging investments in RES, particularly PVB systems. In both cases, prosumers generate electricity for self-consumption and are compensated for surplus energy exported to the grid. The difference lies in how this surplus is valued. Under net metering, excess electricity is credited against future consumption at the retail rate, while under net billing it is credited at a lower rate, reflecting the actual cost of grid services and energy balancing [8]. In recent years, a transition from net metering to net billing has taken place for many countries and regions, driven by concerns about grid sustainability, the real cost of energy balancing, and the need for more equitable compensation frameworks [9]. For example, in Poland, the shift was driven by EU regulatory changes aimed at improving energy self-sufficiency and reducing energy poverty [10]. In Southeast Asia, net billing is being considered to create more equitable policies and address utility revenue impacts [11]. Similar policy transitions are also emerging across Europe, including Greece, where net billing has recently replaced net metering as part of the national regulatory framework. By offering lower compensation for exported electricity, net billing encourages prosumers to prioritize self-consumption and optimize both energy production and storage strategies.

A substantial body of literature has examined the economic assessment and capacity optimization of PVB systems under varying regulatory frameworks and compensation policies. Han et al. [12] conducted a techno-economic optimization of PVB systems in residential groups of Switzerland considering available subsidies, Distribution System Operator (DSO) injection tariffs and tax rebates. They found that the most attractive investment opportunities are within areas of higher annual solar irradiation and electricity demand, with optimal investment sizing ranging from 2 kW to 12.3 kW for the PV and 0 kWh to 12.5 kWh for the battery. Similarly, Schopfer et al. [13] assessed the economic performance of PVB systems under 4190 household electricity consumption profiles and different technology cost scenarios. Considering a steady compensation rate, they concluded that for the current cost scenario, 40% of the studied cases resulted in a positive NPV for a PV system, while for the most optimistic cost scenario, 99.9% of the households benefit from a PVB system installation. Wei et al. [14] analyzed the cost-effectiveness of near-net zero energy buildings (near-NZEB) in California considering PVB and different compensation rates for exported energy in the modeling. They concluded that time-dependent electricity rates improve the cost-effectiveness of near-NZEB homes when coupled with battery storage. Domenech et al. [15] evaluated the performance of PVB installations for either maximum profitability or self-sufficiency. The results showed that variations in load profiles significantly affect PV system size and profitability with optimal installed capacity varying from 1 to 6 kW and NPV reaching a value of 7586€, while maximizing self-sufficiency results in an NPV close to 0 with double-sized PV and small batteries (≤ 3 kWh). Hassan et al. [16] presented an optimization model to assess the techno-economic benefits of coupling battery storage with PV systems under a feed-in tariff (FiT) incentive, based on different electricity rates and battery storage costs. Using real data and simulations, they evaluated the effect of battery capacity on FiT revenue maximization and concluded that battery integration becomes economically viable at costs below 138€/kWh. The different effects of the Net Metering and Net Billing pricing schemes were highlighted by Watts et al. [8], who performed annual simulations of residential PV systems across 10 regions of Chile. Among their results, they concluded that for the case of Net Billing oversized PV systems resulted in worse economic performance. However, this study did not consider the integration of a battery storage system. Wu et al. [17] proposed a new energy management strategy for PV-battery systems, optimizing battery capacity and improving techno-economic performance by integrating self-consumption, peak shifting, and price arbitrage, and highlighted the impact of charging/discharging ratios on system performance. The proposed strategy reduced the total operational cost of the PV-battery system by 682,714 CNY and increased the self-consumption rate by 4.99%. Finally, Hoffman et al. [18] provided an analytical insight on framework-based energy system models and created a mathematical formulation for energy system optimization to serve as a reference for future model development. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that compensation policies, system size, and battery storage are critical factors in optimizing PVB systems. Effective optimization not only strengthens the economic case for prosumer self-production but also mitigates challenges associated with the temporal mismatch between solar generation and demand peaks, thereby facilitating more efficient and reliable energy distribution within the building sector.

The present study advances research on distributed PVB systems by integrating detailed building operation modeling with investment optimization under the recently introduced Greek net-billing framework. While prior studies have often focused separately on either system sizing or tariff comparison, this work develops a unified and policy-oriented modeling framework that explicitly couples dynamic building load simulations with mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) optimization to determine optimal system capacities and operation schedules. Through this coupling, the framework captures the complex interplay between building usage, pricing schemes, and energy self-consumption dynamics, linking realistic load profiles with time-varying electricity prices and operational constraints. The approach reflects real market conditions, incorporating both actual tariff structures and representative

building operation profiles, thereby providing a comprehensive and transferable tool for techno-economic evaluation of renewable energy investments in Mediterranean contexts. Specifically, the study introduces the following innovative elements.

- Scenario-based optimization framework, that combines detailed building simulations with MILP to jointly evaluate technical performance, self-consumption, and economic feasibility across usage and pricing variations. This bridges the gap between physical modeling and policy assessment, providing actionable insights for investors and regulators.
- Comprehensive tariff modeling, incorporating three representative pricing schemes, namely: flat, dual-zone time-of-use (ToU), and real-time pricing (RTP). The RTP profile is derived from actual Greek wholesale market data, replacing the synthetic or rule-based tariffs commonly found in literature, and capturing true market volatility and its effect on PVB operation and profitability. To ensure comparability, all tariffs are normalized to a common mean price, isolating the influence of temporal price variability from average energy cost.
- Detailed representation of building operation, covering residential, retail, and office uses—the main electricity demand segments in Greece and Europe. Each case includes occupancy, appliances, lighting, and domestic hot water (DHW), with comfort-driven temperature setpoints ensuring realistic and physically consistent load behavior.
- Sensitivity analysis evaluating the robustness of optimal configurations under varying retail and feed-in price levels. This reveals how tariff or market shifts affect investment decisions and identifies thresholds influencing PV and battery sizing.

Together, these elements create a replicable and policy-relevant framework that captures the interplay between building operation, user behavior, and tariff design, an aspect often simplified in prior studies. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to quantify the techno-economic implications of Greece's net-billing scheme, providing clear insights for both policymakers and market stakeholders.

2. Materials and methods

This section outlines the theoretical background, describes the reference building system under consideration, and defines the corresponding scenarios. The overall methodology is structured into four key steps, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Step 1 defines the reference building, specifying its geometry, envelope properties, and integrated energy systems (i.e., heat pump). Step 2 computes the electrical loads for three representative building uses: residential, retail and office; the dynamic simulations are based on hourly occupancy, appliance, lighting, and DHW profiles. Step 3 performs the investment optimization, applying the net-billing framework under three retail pricing schemes (flat, dual-zone ToU, and RTP) to determine the cost-optimal PV and battery capacities for each building type. Finally, Step 4 compares the results in terms of optimal system sizing, dispatch behavior, and overall economic performance, complemented by a sensitivity analysis. This structured workflow ensures methodological transparency and facilitates reproducibility across diverse operating and tariff conditions.

2.1. Building model

The present section details the configuration of the reference building adopted in the study, detailing its geometric, thermal, and electrical characteristics, as well as the assumptions regarding building usage and simulation setup.

2.1.1. Building envelope and systems

The reference building considered in this study represents a newly constructed, energy-efficient structure designed in accordance with the Greek Building Energy Performance Regulation (KENAK) [19] and assumed to invest in PVB systems. The building heating and cooling demands are met by heat pump, a configuration consistent with the ongoing electrification of the building sector and aligned with national and European decarbonization targets [20]. This assumption reflects a realistic technological pathway for future building energy systems across different building uses. Moreover, the Mediterranean climate of Greece offers favorable temperature conditions that enhance heat pump efficiency, thereby strengthening their suitability as a cost-effective and low-emission solution for both residential and tertiary buildings [21].

Fig. 1. Followed methodology for the assessment of PVB systems in buildings.

The case building is a detached, two-story, south-oriented structure with a flat roof, located in Athens. It features a simple rectangular geometry ($10 \text{ m} \times 7.5 \text{ m}$, total height 6 m) adopted to facilitate the analysis and ensure that the results remain generalizable and not influenced by architectural complexity. The treated floor area is 130.2 m^2 and the net volume 384.1 m^3 . The average window-to-wall ratio is 20.3%, with the largest openings placed on the southern façade to maximize solar gains. A visual representation of the reference building is provided in Fig. 2.

The building features reinforced concrete roof and ground slabs and double-row brick walls with reinforced concrete integration, fully insulated according to its location and the requirements of Greek legislation [19]. The envelope components comply with the maximum permissible thermal transmittance values for new constructions in the respective climatic zone. The thermal transmittance (U-value) of the construction elements is $0.50 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for walls, $0.45 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for the roof, $0.90 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for the ground slab, and $3.0 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for the windows. The total solar energy transmittance (G-value) is 0.6 for the roof and 0.8 for the walls. Infiltration is considered equal to 0.4 air changes per hour (ACH). The air-to-air split units (heat pumps) have a seasonal coefficient of performance (SCOP) of 3.0 for heating and an energy efficiency ratio (EER) of 3.0 for cooling [22]. A controller is employed to operate the heating and cooling systems only when the building is occupied, while DHW preparation is covered by electrical heating elements. The mean temperature of the utility water is considered $18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the DHW setpoint is considered at $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All geometric and thermal characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

From an electrical perspective, the PV array and battery storage are connected to the building's main AC bus through a bidirectional inverter, enabling energy exchange between generation, storage, and consumption units. The electrical loads include appliances, lighting, and heating or cooling demands, which vary according to building usage and operational schedules. The building interfaces with the external grid via a smart meter that records bidirectional power flows under the net-billing framework. The capacities of the PV system, battery, and inverter are determined through the optimization process.

2.1.2. Building usage

The present section describes the key operational parameters considered for each building category included in the analysis. The study focuses on three representative building usages: residential, retail, and office, which together capture the dominant segments of urban and peri-urban electricity demand profiles in Greece. These categories were selected because they represent the majority of electricity consumption in the European building stock. According to the Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE) [23], residential, office, and retail buildings collectively account for nearly 80% of total final electricity use in buildings across the EU. Their inclusion therefore ensures that the results are directly relevant to the main user groups participating in net billing schemes and reflect the most significant end-use sectors in the Greek context.

The temperature setpoints for each examined case were determined through inverse calculations based on thermal comfort criteria, aiming for a Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) value of zero, corresponding to neutral thermal comfort. The PMV index predicts the mean value of the thermal sensation votes of a large group of occupants on a seven-point scale ranging from -3 (cold) to $+3$ (hot), with 0 representing thermal neutrality [24]. The PMV is calculated as follows [25,26]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PMV} = & (0.303 \cdot e^{-0.036 \cdot M} + 0.028) \{ (M - W) - 3.05 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (5733.0 - 6.99 \cdot (M - W) - p) - 0.42 \cdot ((M - W) - 58.15) \\ & - 1.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M \cdot (5867.0 - p) - 0.0014 \cdot M \cdot (34.0 - T_{\text{air}}) - 3.96 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot f_{\text{cl}} \cdot ((T_{\text{cl}} + 273.15)^4 - (T_r + 273.15)^4) \\ & - f_{\text{cl}} \cdot h_c \cdot (T_{\text{cl}} - T_{\text{air}}) \} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where M denotes the metabolic rate [W/m^2], W represents the effective mechanical power [W/m^2], T_{air} is the room air temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$], p is the partial water vapor pressure [Pa], f_{cl} is the clothing surface area factor, T_r is the mean radiant temperature, which is considered equal to the air temperature in the present calculations [$^\circ\text{C}$], and T_{cl} is the clothing surface temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]. The clothing surface factor f_{cl} depends on the clothing insulation I_{cl} [$\text{m}^2\text{K/W}$], and is defined as follows [24]:

$$f_{\text{cl}} = \begin{cases} 1 + 1.29 \cdot I_{\text{cl}}, & \text{for } I_{\text{cl}} \leq 0.078 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W} \\ 1.05 + 0.645 \cdot I_{\text{cl}}, & \text{for } I_{\text{cl}} > 0.078 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Reference building geometry; a) isometric view and b) floor plan of the 1st floor.

Table 1
Considered geometric and thermal characteristics for the considered building.

Parameter		Value
Location		Athens, 37.9838° N - 23.7275° E
Height (m)		6
Area (m ²)	Walls	165.5
	Floor/roof	75
	Windows	44.5
Thermal transmittance U-value (W/m ² K)	Walls	0.50
	Roof	0.45
	Ground	0.90
	Windows	3
	Roof	0.6
Total solar energy transmittance G-value (–)	Walls	0.8
Infiltration (ACH)		0.4
Heat pump (–)	SCOP	3
	EER	3
Mean temperature of the utility water (°C)		18
DHW setpoint (°C)		45

The metabolic rates (met) and clothing insulation levels (clo) adopted for each building usage and season are presented in Table 2, along with the resulting temperature setpoints derived for a PMV \approx 0. The selected values are consistent with the comfort ranges defined in ASHRAE Standard 55:2020 [27].

The rest of the operational parameters were derived and adapted from EN 16798-1:2019 [28] and EN 12831-3:2017 [29], which provide standardized values for occupancy densities, internal gains, and service requirements across typical building categories. The corresponding parameters applied for each use case are summarized in Table 3, while Fig. 3 presents the weekly operational profiles employed for the occupancy, appliances usage, lighting and DHW consumption. These profiles are periodically repeated throughout the year to maintain consistency with the referenced standards and to ensure comparability across building usages and simulation scenarios.

The combination of standardized input parameters and representative operating profiles ensures that the simulated building loads reflect realistic and comparable conditions across all examined use cases. This approach enables a consistent evaluation of PVB system performance under the net billing framework and provides a robust basis for interpreting the influence of building usage on system sizing, operation, and economic viability.

2.1.3. Simulation setup

Dynamic simulations were performed to determine the energy needs associated with each building usage. Simulations were carried out using the INTEMA software, which performs dynamic building energy performance simulations based on the Modelica language. This tool is well-suited for detailed dynamic studies, employing advanced component-based models for building envelopes and energy systems (e.g., heat pumps, solar thermal collectors). Fig. 4 illustrates the developed system model for the reference building. The model includes components representing the thermal zone, building elements (such as walls, slabs, and windows), ambient weather conditions, internal heat gains, and more. For a comprehensive description of the mathematical framework underpinning the energy calculations further details on the tool, readers are referred to the relevant studies [22,30–32].

The described parameters were used to parameterize the model and perform four annual simulations with hourly resolution, one for each building usage scenario. The climatic conditions employed in this study correspond to the historical meteorological year 2024, retrieved from PVGIS [33] and presented in Fig. 5. As 2024 was a leap year, the additional day was excluded from the dataset to maintain consistency across simulations. The results include time series for all relevant physical quantities, such as heating and cooling loads, DHW consumption, internal gains, and PV system energy yield. These results will be summarized and discussed in Section 3.1.

2.2. Net billing scheme

The quantitative assessment of the net-billing scheme requires explicit parameterization of the retail and export tariffs that govern

Table 2
Representative values of metabolic rate (met), clothing insulation (clo), and resulting temperature setpoints for different building uses (based on ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 [27]).

Building use	Residential		Retail		Office	
	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
Season						
Metabolic rate [W/m ²]	1.0		1.4		1.1	
Clothing insulation [clo]	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
Temperature setpoints [°C]	21	24	18	22	20	24
Notes	Seated or light activity/Normal home clothing		Standing, light activity/Customer-worker average		Seated, typing or writing/Business attire	

Table 3
Building usage parameters.

Building Parameters	Residential	Retail	Office
Occupancy density (persons/m ²)	0.05	0.14	0.10
Number of occupants	6	18	13
Heat gain per occupant (W/person)	80	90	80
Appliance power density (W/m ²)	4	10	12
Lighting power density (W/m ²)	4	10	14
Ventilation (ACH)	0.2	0.8	1
DHW consumption (L/person)	50	5	10

Fig. 3. Weekly usage profiles a) occupancy, b) appliances, c) lighting, and d) DHW consumption [28,29].

energy exchanges with the grid. The following subsections describe the regulatory context and the data-driven formulation of these tariffs, which serve as key input parameters to the optimization model.

2.2.1. Regulatory background

The shift toward decentralized electricity generation has elevated prosumption (i.e., the simultaneous production and consumption of energy) to a central pillar of the EU's energy policy. This trend has been implemented across Member States through diverse national frameworks that encourage small-scale renewable generation and local energy participation [34]. In this context, Greece has emerged as one of the most progressive EU countries in promoting prosumer-oriented policies. By 2015, prosumer electricity generation had already reached an installed capacity of 1.17 GW, demonstrating the country's early engagement in distributed renewable energy development [34,35]. This achievement, however, followed a gradual evolution shaped by successive regulatory frameworks over nearly three decades. For more than twenty years, the feed-in tariff (FiT) regime, first established under Law 2244/1994 [36], served as the primary national policy supporting renewable electricity production by individuals and enterprises. The FiT system guaranteed long-term purchase agreements at fixed rates, successfully accelerating the diffusion of RES within the national electricity mix. Despite its success in promoting early adoption, the FiT model offered limited incentives for active energy management or self-consumption, as all production was sold to the grid.

The country's transition toward self-consumption models began with the introduction of the net-metering (NEM) scheme in 2013, later complemented by the virtual net-metering (vNEM) extension [37]. Under NEM, energy consumers (either individuals or legal entities) could offset their electricity consumption against the electricity produced by their own renewable installations, primarily photovoltaics and small wind systems. The framework operated on a three-year billing cycle: if a consumer's cumulative production exceeded consumption during this period, the surplus was credited to subsequent bills; otherwise, the consumer was charged for the net difference [38].

Although NEM proved beneficial for prosumers, its long settlement period effectively used the grid as a “virtual storage” system,

Fig. 4. Developed building system model in the Modelica environment.

Fig. 5. Ambient temperature and horizontal solar irradiation for the city of Athens.

decoupling consumption from real-time market conditions. This characteristic, combined with the maturing renewable market and evolving EU directives, motivated a policy shift toward more dynamic compensation mechanisms. In response, Greece officially transitioned from NEM to net billing (NEB) under the Ministerial Decision published in the Government Gazette (5074B/September 05, 2024). The NEB framework introduces real-time energy balancing and market-based compensation for surplus electricity exported to the grid, aligning national policy with EU objectives for flexible, consumer-centric energy markets. Under the new scheme, small-scale RES systems (mainly PV installations) can now offset their production and consumption on an hourly basis. The exported surplus is compensated financially at market rates derived from wholesale electricity prices, replacing the long-term crediting mechanism of NEM. The NEB scheme also supports virtual net billing (vNEB), allowing generation and consumption to take place at different sites under the same ownership, thereby expanding the flexibility and inclusiveness of the prosumer framework.

From a technical perspective, the legislation sets specific capacity limits depending on user type. For residential prosumers, the maximum installed capacity is 10.8 kW per supply point, while for legal entities under public or private law, the limit extends up to 100 kW. Special provisions are included for agricultural producers and energy communities, reflecting the growing role of collective prosumer initiatives in local energy planning. In terms of financial compensation, the regulation provides two main categories. For installations up to 1 MWe, a fixed reference price of 0.066 €/kWh applies to the surplus electricity injected into the grid without requiring participation in a competitive tender. For larger installations (>1 MWe), the compensation rate can be negotiated bilaterally

between the prosumer and the retail company. These pricing structures encourage investments in distributed generation while promoting battery integration to increase self-consumption and grid autonomy. Finally, both NEB and vNEB agreements are defined to have a duration of 20 years, ensuring long-term stability and investor confidence. Together, these provisions mark a decisive step in Greece's transition toward a more market-integrated, decentralized, and consumer-driven electricity system.

2.2.2. Tariff formulation for modeling

Because investment outcomes and operational performance are directly influenced by retail price formation, three representative tariff structures are modeled in this study: flat, dual-zone ToU, and RTP. The values and temporal profiles of these tariffs are critical, as they directly determine the optimization of the PVB system. Each tariff was constructed through a transparent, data-driven procedure consistent with current Greek practice and forthcoming regulatory changes.

For consistency across all tariff types, the hourly retail price P_t^{retail} is formulated as the sum of three components [39]:

$$P_t^{\text{retail}} = P_t^{\text{energy}} + P_t^{\text{network}} + P_t^{\text{tax}}, \quad (3)$$

where P_t^{energy} represents the energy and supply costs, including the retailer's profit margin (typically accounting for 65-75% of the retail bill), P_t^{network} corresponds to the regulated transmission and distribution charges (i.e., Transmission Use-of-System (TUoS)/Distribution Use-of-System (DUoS)), and P_t^{tax} includes policy levies and value-added tax VAT. Based on representative Greek household invoices for 2024, these network and policy components together amount to approximately 40% on top of the energy component, corresponding to an energy share of about 70 % of the final retail price. Accordingly, all tariff structures were derived by first estimating P_t^{energy} and then applying a 1.4 multiplication factor to represent network, policy, and tax-related surcharges. This ensures that the final prices used in the optimization reflect the full retail cost faced by consumers.

2.2.2.1. Flat tariff. The flat tariff represents constant-rate retail contracts currently offered in Greece. The underlying energy component P_t^{energy} was set at 0.130 €/kWh, corresponding to the prevailing 2024 market level. After applying the 40% markup, the resulting final retail price used in the optimization is:

$$P_t^{\text{retail}} = 1.4 \times 0.130 = 0.183 \text{ €/kWh}$$

2.2.2.2. Dual-zone ToU tariff. The ToU structure follows the bi-zonal schedule defined by the Greek Distribution System Operator (HEDNO) [40], with low-price periods during night hours and extended midday blocks. The representative retail levels used are:

$$\text{Off – peak : } P_t^{\text{energy}} = 0.093 \text{ €/kWh} \Rightarrow P_t^{\text{retail}} = 0.130 \text{ €/kWh}$$

$$\text{Peak : } P_t^{\text{energy}} = 0.149 \text{ €/kWh} \Rightarrow P_t^{\text{retail}} = 0.209 \text{ €/kWh}$$

2.2.2.3. Real-time pricing (RTP) tariff. No active retail RTP product currently exists in Greece, as the regulatory framework (“orange bill”) is still under preparation [41]. Therefore, a pass-through approach was adopted, directly linking hourly wholesale electricity prices to the retail level, consistent with existing European schemes such as Octopus Agile (UK) and Tibber (Nordic countries) [42]. The representative RTP series was generated through the following steps.

1. Wholesale data acquisition: Hourly Day-Ahead Market (DAM) prices p_t for 2024 are collected.
2. Monthly alignment: To ensure consistency with supplier-reported Weighted Average Market Prices (MTA) [40], a monthly scaling factor s_m is applied:

$$\bar{p} = \frac{1}{|H_m|} \sum_{t \in H_m} p_t \quad (4)$$

$$s_m = \frac{\text{MTA}_m}{\bar{p}} \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{p}_t = s_m \cdot p_t \quad (t \in H_m) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{p} is the mean hourly wholesale price within month m , p_t the original hourly wholesale price (€/kWh), H_m the set of all hourly timestamps in month m , s_m the monthly scaling factor (–), \tilde{p}_t the MTA-aligned hourly electricity price (€/kWh).

3. Price capping: To avoid unrealistic spikes during extreme market conditions, the scaled wholesale price was first capped at a maximum value of 0.60 €/kWh

$$P_t^{\text{cap}} = \min(\tilde{p}_t, P_{\text{cap}}) \quad (7)$$

4. Retail price formation: The capped hourly price was then multiplied by 1.4 to account for network charges, policy levies, and VAT:

$$P_t^{\text{retail}} = 1.4 \times P_t^{\text{cap}} \tag{8}$$

This sequence ensures that the capping reflects wholesale market behavior before surcharges are applied, while the resulting retail series remains consistent with observed consumer price structures.

Fig. 6 presents the hourly evolution of the three tariff schemes. The flat tariff remains constant at 0.183 €/kWh, while the ToU tariff alternates between 0.130 €/kWh (off-peak) and 0.209 €/kWh (peak). The RTP profile, derived from wholesale data and processed as described above, exhibits pronounced temporal variability, with hourly values typically ranging between 0.04 €/kWh and 0.55 €/kWh after applying the cap. Quantitatively, the standard deviation of hourly prices is 0.098 €/kWh for the RTP scheme, compared to 0.037 €/kWh for the ToU tariff and nearly zero for the flat tariff. This corresponds to coefficients of variation (CV) of approximately 53.7%, 20.5%, and 0%, respectively, clearly demonstrating the much stronger volatility introduced by dynamic pricing. The inset of Fig. 6 illustrates a representative week, clearly showing the limited variability of static tariffs compared to the strong intra-day oscillations of RTP, which enable enhanced flexibility, demand response, and battery-operation optimization under dynamic market conditions.

2.3. Investment optimization

The optimal capacities and dispatch are evaluated using the investment optimization problem, formulated as a MILP problem using the PyPSA module in Python [43]. The problem considers the investment costs and compares the usage of existing components against building up new capacity. The objective is to determine the optimal system configuration, including both the capacities and the operational (dispatch) strategy that minimizes total costs, while meeting energy demand. The main assumptions of the optimization problem are perfect foresight, the fulfillment of energy demand at each timestamp (referred to as inelastic demand), and that all producers and consumers act as price takers (i.e., no entity can exert market power), thereby ensuring perfect competition.

In its general form, the objective function is set to minimize the system cost (SC), which is composed of capital expenditures (CAPEX) c for each component of the system and operation expenditures (OPEX) o for each generator unit g :

$$\text{minimise } SC = \sum_{n,s} c_{n,s} \bar{g}_{n,s} + \sum_{n,s} c_{n,s} \bar{h}_{n,s} + \sum_t \omega_t \left[\sum_{n,s} o_{n,s,t} g_{n,s,t} + \sum_{n,s} o_{n,s,t} h_{n,s,t} \right] \tag{9}$$

where n is the bus index, t is the snapshot, l is the branches and s is the label for the different generator or storage types at each bus. Also, \bar{g} and \bar{h} are the nominal capacities for extendable generators and storages respectively, $g_{n,s,t}$ the dispatch of generator s , and $h_{n,s,t}$ the storage dispatch (when it depletes the state of charge). Conceptually, in Equation (9), the first two terms pertain to the capital costs necessary for the expansion of generators and storage, while the subsequent term regards the operation, i.e. the marginal costs of generators and storage. Renewable generators, i.e. PV generation is defined as a per unit (pu) dimensionless curve for typical solar power generation in a particular location. It is inserted as pu and the algorithm scales it accordingly to determine the optimal capacity. Additionally, the energy capacity of the storage unit (battery) is expressed relative to its power capacity in hours, representing the hours required for the storage unit to charge or discharge at its nominal power.

Investment optimization typically requires a multi-year analysis to assess the economic viability of the system, accounting for the long-term dynamics of costs, revenues, and system performance. However, to simplify this process and reduce computational complexity, a common approach is to use annualized capital costs [18]. This method condenses the total investment cost of new capacity into a uniform annual expense, allowing the analysis to focus on a single representative year. The annualized capital costs are calculated using the formula, where r and n correspond to discount rate and asset lifetime, respectively:

Fig. 6. Hourly electricity price profile for the three examined tariffs (i.e., flat, dual-zone ToU, and RTP) over a full year. The inset highlights a representative week, illustrating the low variability of the flat and ToU tariffs compared to the high temporal fluctuations of the RTP profile derived from wholesale market data.

$$\text{Annualized CAPEX} = \text{CAPEX} \frac{r(1+r)^n}{(1+r)^n - 1} \quad (10)$$

The parameters considered in the optimization are presented in Table 4, along with their corresponding references. Among these, the most critical are the discount rate, the CAPEX of the two modules, their lifetimes, and the energy feed-in tariff to the grid. It is important to note that the assumed CAPEX values for the technologies include the costs of power electronics and the balance of the system. Additionally, zero OPEX has been assumed due to the small scale of the installation systems.

It should also be emphasized that the MILP formulation applied in this study is not intended for real-time control of PVB systems. Due to its computational complexity and extensive data requirements, MILP is not practical for operational decision-making in actual installations. Instead, it is employed here as a research and planning tool, providing a robust framework for system sizing, investment assessment, and the evaluation of techno-economic potential under different scenarios.

3. Results

This section presents the main findings obtained through the application of the proposed methodology. The results are organized by topic, beginning with the analysis of building electrical loads, followed by the determination of optimal system capacities and dispatch patterns for each examined scenario. In total, three building usage types and three electricity pricing schemes are analyzed, resulting in nine distinct cases. In addition, the results of the price and smoothness sensitivity analyses are discussed to further illustrate the influence of tariff structure and volatility on the techno-economic performance of PVB systems.

3.1. Electrical loads

The initial step of the methodology involves calculating the electrical loads for all cases through dynamic simulations using the INTEMA software, which is based on the Modelica language. These simulations generate hourly time series of power demand, forming the foundation for the subsequent investment optimization analyses. Fig. 7 presents the aggregated annual electrical demand (in MWh/year) broken down by end-use categories across building types. Retail buildings exhibit the highest total demand, driven predominantly by appliances, which reflect the continuous operation of high-capacity refrigeration and display equipment, including during nighttime hours. Cooling contributes a secondary share, while heating and DHW are minor. Office buildings show an intermediate total load; appliances remain the dominant category, though at a lower level than in retail, as there is minimal need for operation during night. Residential buildings register the lowest overall demand, with a more evenly distributed profile. DHW constitutes the largest share, highlighting its critical role in household energy consumption, followed closely by appliances. Heating and cooling are also significant, driven by the need for continuous space conditioning. Importantly, both the relative order and the magnitude of the resulting end-uses are consistent with actual measurements reported for representative Greek buildings, confirming the realism of the adopted usage profiles and operational assumptions [49].

Fig. 8 presents the monthly electrical energy demand for the three building usages, highlighting the clear influence of building function and seasonality on consumption levels. Retail buildings consistently exhibit the highest energy demand throughout the year, with pronounced summer peaks driven by intensified cooling loads and continuous operation of lighting and refrigeration systems. Office buildings follow, showing moderate annual variation with slightly elevated consumption during summer months due to air-conditioning requirements and higher occupancy. Residential buildings maintain the lowest overall demand, characterized by a relatively stable profile and mild seasonal fluctuation. Their winter consumption slightly exceeds summer levels, reflecting heating and DHW needs, while summer values remain moderate due to lower appliance and cooling usage. These trends confirm the strong link between building function, internal gains, and climate-driven energy needs.

Fig. 9 presents the hourly energy demand profiles for the three examined building usages over representative winter and summer weeks. Distinct temporal patterns emerge, reflecting the combined effects of occupancy schedules and climatic conditions. Office and retail buildings have distinct working-hour patterns, with high daytime demand and very low consumption at night and during weekends when they are mostly closed. Office demand is highly concentrated within working hours, whereas retail shows a broader activity window extending into the evening. Residential demand, in contrast, exhibits smaller daytime variations but maintains a consistently higher baseline due to continuous occupancy and DHW use, with evening peaks driven by appliance operation. Seasonal differences are pronounced, particularly for commercial buildings, where summer cooling loads cause peak power demands exceeding 5 kW, compared to approximately 4 kW in winter.

From this analysis, it can be inferred that the simulations yielded results consistent with the expected behavior of the three

Table 4
Techno-economic parameters considered in investment optimization.

Parameter	Value	
Discount rate [%]	5 [44]	
CAPEX [€/kW]	1200 [45]	Photovoltaic
Lifetime [y]	25 [44]	Battery
Feed-in tariff [€/kWh]	0.066 [48]	1600 [46] (400 €/kWh)
Inverter efficiency [%]	98 [12]	8 [47]

Fig. 7. Total electrical loads per building usage.

Fig. 8. Monthly electrical load variations for the examined building usages.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Hourly power demand for the three building usage profiles for indicative (a) winter, and (b) summer weeks.

examined building types. These differentiated profiles are critical for determining the optimal PV and battery capacities, as they directly influence the potential for self-consumption, storage utilization, and economic performance.

3.2. Optimal capacities and dispatch

The next step includes determining the optimal capacities for each case. As detailed in Section 2.2, three electricity pricing schemes are examined, namely flat tariff, dual-zone ToU and RTP. For each scenario, the optimal PV and battery capacities are identified, and the hourly energy dispatch is analyzed. Then, a sensitivity analysis is performed to assess how price levels and volatility affect system performance under net-billing conditions.

3.2.1. Flat tariff

Table 5 presents the investment optimization results for the flat tariff scenario (0.183 €/kWh). Under a uniform electricity price, there is no temporal incentive for load shifting, so profitability depends mainly on how effectively PV production can offset imports within each usage profile and on the low export compensation (0.066 €/kWh). Consequently, the optimization consistently favors configurations that maximize direct self-consumption rather than oversizing systems for grid exports. Residential buildings achieve the highest self-consumption (40.4%) with moderate system capacities (2.96 kW PV and 3.29 kWh battery). Their continuous operation and evening demand support a balanced utilization of on-site generation and storage. Retail buildings, characterized by extended daytime activity and intensive lighting and appliance loads, justify larger installations (5.28 kW PV and 7.73 kWh battery) while achieving a comparable self-consumption rate (40.1%). In contrast, office buildings exhibit lower total electricity consumption and shorter operating hours (compared to retail), resulting in minimal system sizes (0.47 kW PV and 0.52 kWh battery) and a self-consumption ratio of only 5.5%. The limited daily operation and weekend inactivity restrict opportunities for on-site utilization, while the low remuneration for exported electricity further discourages investment. Despite the observed differences in system sizing and load alignment, the payback periods remain relatively similar across all building types, ranging between 6 and 7 years.

Fig. 10 illustrates the temporal evolution of load, PV generation, battery operation, and grid exchange for the three examined building usages under the flat tariff scenario. The distinct profiles highlight how operational schedules and load characteristics shape the interaction between local generation and grid dependency. Retail buildings show the most pronounced battery cycling, with frequent charge–discharge activity driven by continuous daytime operation and higher, more predictable loads. In residential buildings, the battery operates less intensively, as evening demand peaks coincide with periods of low PV generation, limiting charging opportunities and resulting in more sporadic battery use. Grid imports dominate during nighttime, winter months, and mid-summer periods with high cooling loads, while exports occur mainly around midday when PV generation exceeds local consumption. Exports are particularly evident in retail buildings due to their higher PV capacities, whereas office installations exhibit negligible PV and battery activity, reflecting their limited energy demand and short operating schedule. These dispatch patterns confirm that under a flat tariff, the optimization primarily aims to offset direct grid imports without temporal shifting of demand, leading to modest battery utilization.

3.2.2. Dual-zone ToU

Table 6 summarizes the investment optimization outcomes for the dual-zone ToU tariff, where electricity is priced at 0.130 €/kWh during off-peak and 0.209 €/kWh during peak hours. Compared to the flat tariff case, this structure introduces a modest temporal signal that rewards consumption or discharge during high-price periods and incentivizes energy shifting. Thus, the optimization algorithm adapts both PV and storage capacities to exploit the price differential while maintaining economically viable investment levels. Residential buildings continue to favor relatively large PVB systems (4.05 kW PV and 9.83 kWh battery), achieving a self-consumption rate of 58.2%. The higher storage capacity compared to the flat-tariff case reflects the benefit of shifting surplus midday generation to the evening peak period, when electricity prices are higher. This strategy increases annual savings (1427 €) while maintaining a short payback period of 6.2 years. Retail buildings derive the greatest advantage from the ToU structure, as their extended daytime operation coincides with the high-tariff period. Consequently, the optimizer selects the largest system (6.04 kW PV and 15.94 kWh battery), yielding a self-consumption rate of 50.5%, annual savings of 2128 €, and a payback period of 6.4 years. Office buildings exhibit a notable improvement compared to the flat-tariff scenario, with capacities rising to 2.41 kW PV and 9.6 kWh battery and a self-consumption ratio of 25.7%. However, their shorter operating hours and weekend inactivity still limit economic performance, resulting in a longer payback of 7.9 years.

Across all building types, the ToU structure results in slightly higher investment costs, primarily due to larger battery capacities. These additional costs are largely offset by the corresponding increase in annual savings. The results confirm that even a simple dual-zone tariff can improve the profitability of PVB systems by rewarding strategic storage operation. Nevertheless, the overall gains

Table 5
Optimum results for each building usage for the flat tariff scenario.

Building Usage	PV (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Electricity Import (kWh)	Self-Consumption (%)	Total Capex (€)	Annual Savings (€)	Payback Period (years)
Residential	2.96	3.29	6055	40.44	4864	793	6.13
Retail	5.28	7.73	9862	40.07	9434	1334	7.07
Office	0.47	0.52	11306	5.48	771	126	6.11

Fig. 10. Load, PV generation, battery operation, and grid exchange for the optimal PVB configurations in the examined (a) residential, (b) retail, and (c) office buildings under the flat tariff scenario.

Table 6

Optimum results for each building usage for the dual-zone ToU tariff.

Building Usage	PV (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Electricity Import (kWh)	Self-Consumption (%)	Total Capex (€)	Annual Savings (€)	Payback Period (years)
Residential	4.05	9.83	4252	58.17	8795	1427	6.16
Retail	6.04	15.94	8147	50.49	13629	2128	6.4
Office	2.41	9.6	8886	25.71	6733	851	7.91

remain moderate, as the price differential between off-peak and peak hours (≈ 0.08 €/kWh) is relatively small. Consequently, ToU tariffs promote more balanced system sizing and improved alignment between load and generation, yet they still fall short of fully unlocking the flexibility potential that more dynamic pricing schemes can offer.

Following, Fig. 11 illustrates the corresponding dispatch. In all cases, the daily charge/discharge cycles are clearly visible: batteries charge during low-tariff (off-peak) hours and discharge during high-tariff (peak) periods to offset grid imports. This behavior is particularly evident in retail and office buildings, where daytime operation coincides with the high-tariff period, enhancing the

Fig. 11. Load, PV generation, battery operation, and grid exchange for the optimal PVB configurations in the examined (a) residential, (b) retail, and (c) office buildings under the dual-zone ToU scenario.

economic value of stored energy. Residential buildings exhibit smoother and less frequent cycling, as their main demand peaks occur in the evening when PV production is low, limiting the opportunity for full charge/discharge utilization. Retail buildings demonstrate the most pronounced battery use, driven by higher and more consistent daytime loads that align well with PV generation. Office buildings also show increased storage utilization compared to the flat tariff case. Across all building usages, the integration of larger batteries reduces grid imports relative to the flat tariff, particularly during spring and summer when solar availability is high. However, grid dependency remains notable during winter due to reduced solar irradiation and elevated heating demands. The ToU structure enhances the temporal coordination between PV generation, storage, and demand, improving load-generation alignment, resulting in

Table 7
Optimum results for each building usage for the RTP scenario.

Building Usage	PV (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Electricity Import (kWh)	Self-Consumption (%)	Total Capex (€)	Annual Savings (€)	Payback Period (years)
Residential	4.11	10.93	4077	59.89	9305	1420	6.55
Retail	6.38	17.88	7640	53.57	14811	2223	6.66
Office	2.66	13.49	8386	29.89	8592	1056	8.13

significantly higher self-consumption rates.

3.2.3. Real-time pricing (RTP)

Table 7 presents the investment optimization results for the RTP scenario, in which the hourly electricity price typically varies between 0.04 €/kWh and 0.55 €/kWh, maintaining an annual mean of 0.183 €/kWh. This high temporal variability introduces strong incentives for energy shifting, fundamentally altering the optimal design compared to both the flat and dual-zone tariffs. The optimization framework responds to these dynamic signals by favoring configurations capable of arbitraging price fluctuations. Residential buildings achieve the highest self-consumption (59.9%) with a balanced configuration of 4.11 kW PV and 10.93 kWh battery. The larger storage capacity enables energy shifting from midday to high-price evening hours, reducing grid imports and yielding annual savings of 1420 € with a payback period of 6.6 years. Retail buildings also benefit considerably under RTP, as their extended daytime activity coincides with price volatility. The optimizer selects the largest overall system (6.38 kW PV and 17.88 kWh battery), resulting in a self-consumption rate of 53.6% and annual savings of 2223 €. Office buildings, although limited by shorter operating hours, also display a notable increase in system size (2.66 kW PV and 13.49 kWh battery) and a self-consumption ratio of 29.9%, with a payback period of 8.1 years. Compared with the dual-zone ToU case, all building types exhibit substantially higher battery capacities under RTP, reflecting the system's response to strong hourly price fluctuations. However, the larger storage capacities do not result in a

Fig. 12. Load, PV generation, battery operation, and grid exchange for the optimal PVB configurations in the examined (a) residential, (b) retail, and (c) office buildings under the RTP scenario.

proportional increase in self-consumption, indicating that the additional flexibility is mainly used to adapt to hourly price fluctuations rather than to enhance local energy use. This suggests that under RTP conditions, storage primarily serves to buffer price volatility rather than to increase prosumer self-sufficiency.

Fig. 12 presents the optimal dispatch for the three examined building usages under the RTP scenario. Compared with the dual-zone ToU tariff, the battery operation exhibits a far more irregular and adaptive pattern, reflecting the system's response to rapid hourly price fluctuations. The high volatility of the RTP profile drives frequent and sometimes partial charge/discharge events throughout the day, as the system continuously seeks to exploit short-term cost differentials. This behavior is particularly visible in the retail and office cases, where the battery follows closely the price signal to reduce imports during expensive hours and absorb excess generation during low-price periods. Despite the higher installed battery capacities, the impact on the overall electricity exchange remains similar to that observed under the dual-zone tariff. This indicates that while price volatility enhances temporal flexibility, it does not necessarily translate into higher self-consumption or improved energy autonomy.

3.3. Sensitivity analyses

To complement the main optimization results, two additional sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the robustness of the findings and explore how external factors influence the optimal configuration of PVB systems. The first focuses on price sensitivity, examining how variations in electricity cost assumptions affect investment outcomes. The second introduces a smoothness sensitivity analysis, designed to investigate the influence of temporal price volatility on techno-economic performance. Together, these analyses provide a more comprehensive understanding of the parameters that shape system profitability and self-consumption behavior under net-billing conditions.

3.3.1. Price sensitivity analysis

This analysis evaluates the impact of varying electricity price levels on the optimal system configuration. The base retail and feed-in tariffs are multiplied by predefined factors, simulating potential deviations in market prices or policy adjustments. The base retail and feed-in tariffs were scaled by predefined multipliers ranging from 0.8 to 1.2, with a step of 0.1, normalized with respect to the baseline

Fig. 13. Sensitivity analysis of optimal PVB capacities and self-consumption ratios as a function of buy and sell price factors across all tariff schemes and building usages: (a–c) Residential, (d–f) Retail, and (g–i) Office.

values presented in Section 2.2. Each combination of factors represents a possible deviation in market conditions or policy adjustments. For every scenario, the MILP optimization model was executed to determine the cost-optimal PVB capacities, along with the corresponding self-consumption ratio and overall economic performance.

Fig. 13 presents the results of the two-dimensional price sensitivity analysis, illustrating the optimal PVB capacities and corresponding self-consumption ratios as a function of the buy and sell price factors for all tariff schemes and building usages. Across all cases, the optimal PV capacity exhibits a clear positive dependence on the sell price factor, as higher export remuneration incentivizes larger PV installations and greater energy export potential. Conversely, the battery capacity is primarily driven by the buy price factor, as higher import costs enhance the economic value of storage, encouraging temporal load shifting. This opposing behavior emphasizes the synergistic interaction between PV and storage systems, where PV expansion maximizes energy generation while batteries enable temporal balancing and self-consumption optimization.

The impact of pricing structure on system sizing is significant. Under flat tariffs, both PV and battery capacities (and consequently self-consumption) remain low, as constant prices provide weak incentives for either generation expansion or storage investment. The dual-zone ToU and RTP schemes, by contrast, yield similar capacity patterns, both exhibiting higher PV and battery investments compared to the flat case. This similarity indicates that the simplified temporal differentiation of the ToU tariff already captures much of the variability driving prosumer responsiveness under RTP. In the residential case, this effect is especially pronounced, since the ToU schedule closely aligns with typical load and PV generation profiles, i.e., low nighttime consumption and high daytime production, thereby reproducing the key dynamics of RTP without requiring full hourly volatility.

Retail buildings exhibit the highest overall self-consumption, as their daytime operation aligns closely with PV generation, minimizing exports and reducing the need for storage. Residential buildings follow, benefiting from battery installation due to evening demand peaks and greater temporal flexibility. At high buy factors, a saturation plateau emerges, where further increases in electricity cost yield diminishing gains in battery capacity, indicating that the self-consumption potential is nearly fully exploited. Office buildings display the lowest sensitivity, as limited operating hours restrict both the achievable self-consumption and the economic incentive for storage. Across all building types, self-consumption ratios remain consistently higher under dual-zone ToU and RTP tariffs compared to the flat case, confirming that temporal price differentiation enhances on-site energy use. However, beyond certain buy/sell combinations (particularly in residential scenarios) self-consumption reaches a plateau, reflecting the technical limits of demand-generation coincidence and storage utilization within typical daily load cycles.

The price sensitivity analysis reveals that both tariff design and building usage critically shape the optimal configuration and performance of PVB systems under the net-billing framework. The buy and sell price factors govern distinct investment drivers; batteries respond primarily to import costs, while PV installations scale with export remuneration, highlighting the need for balanced policy signals that promote both generation and flexibility. Among the examined tariffs, RTP induces the strongest investment responsiveness and highest self-consumption levels, followed by the dual-zone ToU scheme, whereas the flat tariff consistently yields smaller systems and limited flexibility potential. These findings underscore that temporal price differentiation is essential to unlock the full technical and economic benefits of distributed PVB systems, enabling more adaptive, self-sufficient, and grid-supportive prosumer behavior.

3.3.2. Smoothness sensitivity analysis

In addition to the price sensitivity analysis, a smoothness sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate how the short-term variability of RTP affects system design and profitability. For this purpose, the original hourly RTP profile was progressively smoothed using the Savitzky–Golay filter [50], which performs a local polynomial regression to reduce high-frequency fluctuations while preserving the overall trend and shape of the signal. Three smoothing window lengths were tested: 0 (no smoothing), 20 h, and 40 h, hereafter referred to as *rtp*, *rtp20*, and *rtp40*, respectively. Increasing the smoothing window emulates a gradual reduction of market volatility—representative of potential regulatory interventions that cap extreme hourly price variations. For consistency, all profiles were rescaled to retain the same annual mean price as the original RTP series, thus isolating the effect of volatility from that of average cost differences. This analysis allows assessing whether reducing the temporal volatility of dynamic tariffs benefits or disadvantages prosumers participating in net-billing schemes, providing additional insight into how tariff design influences optimal photovoltaic-battery investments.

Fig. 14 illustrates the effect of RTP smoothing on optimal PV–battery capacities and self-consumption for the three examined building usages. The results clearly demonstrate that price volatility exerts a strong influence on system configuration, particularly on battery sizing, while PV capacity remains largely unaffected. The magnitude of this influence, however, varies across building types. For residential buildings, the high-volatility RTP case (*rtp*) results in a battery capacity of 10.9 kWh, which increases slightly to 11.1 kWh under moderate smoothing (*rtp20*) and declines to 9.8 kWh for the smoother profile (*rtp40*). PV capacity remains nearly constant (≈ 4.1 – 4.4 kW), and self-consumption stays stable around 60%, indicating that residential systems are largely insensitive to short-term price variability. For retail buildings, volatility has a more pronounced impact on system sizing. The highest battery capacity (≈ 19.9 kWh) occurs under moderate volatility (*rtp20*), suggesting that some level of price fluctuation enhances the value of storage. Further smoothing (*rtp40*) reduces the optimal battery size to 15 kWh and slightly decreases self-consumption, reflecting weaker economic signals for flexibility. For office buildings, reduced volatility leads to a substantial downsizing of both PV and storage. Capacities fall from 2.7 kW to 13.5 kWh under the original RTP profile to 1.2 kW and 3.4 kWh under *rtp40*, while self-consumption declines sharply from about 30% to 12%. This pattern is consistent with previous findings under flat and ToU tariffs, where limited operational flexibility and shorter schedules constrain the economic benefit of storage.

The smoothness sensitivity analysis confirms that price volatility directly shapes the economic value of storage. As volatility decreases, battery capacity and profitability diminish, while PV sizing remains almost unchanged. In summary, residential buildings are

Fig. 14. Effect of RTP smoothing on optimal PVB capacities and self-consumption.

largely unaffected by volatility, retail buildings benefit from moderate variability, and office buildings require high volatility to justify battery investment and active participation in flexibility markets.

4. Discussion

The results presented across the three pricing schemes and sensitivity analyses highlight the strong interdependence between tariff structure, building usage, and investment decisions for PVB systems under net-billing framework. While all examined configurations achieve techno-economic feasibility, the driving factors behind optimal sizing, self-consumption, and profitability differ substantially between usage types.

Among all parameters, building usage exerts the most significant influence on both energy behavior and optimal system configuration. Residential buildings display the highest self-consumption levels, consistently around 40–60, supported by balanced PV-to-battery ratios (approximately 4 kW PV/10 kWh battery under dynamic tariffs). Their continuous occupancy and evening demand align well with storage discharge periods, maximizing on-site utilization. Retail buildings, with higher total demand and extended daytime operation, maintain self-consumption rates near 50%, but their larger loads require more extensive PV installations (≈ 6 kW) and higher storage capacities (≈ 16 kWh). Offices, characterized by short operating hours and weekend closure, exhibit the lowest performance, with self-consumption values of only 5–30% across tariffs. These differences confirm that operational flexibility, rather than load magnitude, is the dominant determinant of storage value.

The transition from a flat to a temporally differentiated pricing structure significantly alters the system's optimal configuration. The dual-zone ToU tariff increases self-consumption by roughly 15–20 percentage points compared to the flat tariff, as batteries charge during off-peak hours (0.13 €/kWh) and discharge during high-tariff periods (0.21 €/kWh). This moderate differentiation encourages energy shifting but still constrain flexibility due to the small price spread. In contrast, the RTP scheme, where hourly prices range between 0.04 €/kWh and 0.55 €/kWh, induces slightly larger battery capacities (up to 18 kWh for retail buildings) and more irregular dispatch patterns as the optimizer reacts to hourly volatility. However, these larger capacities do not yield proportionally higher self-consumption, indicating that the additional flexibility primarily mitigates cost exposure during price spikes rather than increasing local utilization. This highlights a key distinction between the two tariff types: ToU tariffs promote predictable operation and stronger alignment between load and PV generation, whereas RTP tariffs drive reactive behavior, with systems adjusting dynamically to minimize electricity costs rather than to improve self-consumption.

Despite clear operational differences between tariffs, the resulting payback periods remain relatively close (approximately 6–8 years). This convergence suggests that within the examined pricing range, investment feasibility is not highly sensitive to the specific tariff structure, as both capital costs and average annual prices dominate the overall economics. Nevertheless, the distribution of costs and benefits varies: under RTP, total investment costs rise by about 20–30% due to higher storage capacity, while the ToU tariff achieves a balanced compromise between economic return and operational complexity. Importantly, the low export remuneration of 0.066 €/kWh remains a limiting factor for all scenarios, reinforcing the importance of maximizing on-site consumption over grid exports.

The price sensitivity analysis further clarifies the distinct economic drivers for PV and battery investments. PV capacity increases primarily with higher feed-in remuneration, while storage responds more strongly to import price levels. This decoupled behavior emphasizes the need for coherent tariff design that simultaneously rewards self-consumption and temporal flexibility. The smoothness sensitivity analysis further confirms that volatility directly shapes storage value: as the RTP signal is progressively smoothed, battery capacity and profitability decline by up to 40%, while PV sizing remains nearly constant. The effect is usage-dependent; residential systems are largely insensitive to volatility, retail buildings perform best under moderate variability, and office systems require high volatility to justify investment. These differentiated responses suggest that tariff design should be tailored to user type, ensuring that flexibility incentives match operational potential.

From a policy and system-integration perspective, the findings underline the critical role of dynamic tariffs in promoting flexible demand and distributed storage within net-billing frameworks. However, excessive volatility may increase operational complexity

without yielding proportional gains in self-consumption, particularly for buildings with rigid load schedules. Therefore, moderate temporal differentiation, such as refined ToU structures calibrated to typical demand patterns, may represent the most balanced approach.

Although the proposed framework provides valuable insights into the techno-economic performance of PVB systems under different tariff structures, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the analysis focuses on a single climatic location (Athens) and uses representative market conditions for the Greek context. This is an inherent limitation, as the study is tailored to national conditions, although the proposed framework can be readily adapted to other contexts. In addition, only three building cases are examined; as discussed in Section 2.1.2, these categories were selected because they represent the majority of electricity consumption in the European building stock. Second, the optimization assumes perfect foresight and static system parameters, neglecting uncertainties in future electricity prices, demand variability, and potential battery degradation over time. Including stochastic or degradation-aware models could improve the long-term accuracy of investment evaluation. Finally, grid-level interactions and local network constraints were not modeled; their inclusion could reveal additional system-level effects, such as export saturation or voltage constraints at high prosumer penetration.

5. Conclusions

The present study quantified how building usage and tariff design shape optimal PVB investments under Greece's net-billing framework. Three usage types (residential, retail, office) and three retail schemes (flat, dual-zone ToU, RTP) were evaluated with dynamic load simulation and MILP sizing/dispatch. The main conclusions are.

- Building usage proved to be the strongest determinant of system performance. Residential buildings achieved the highest self-consumption levels (40–60%) supported by balanced PV-to-battery ratios (≈ 4 kW PV/10 kWh battery). Retail buildings required larger systems (≈ 6 kW PV/16–18 kWh battery) due to their higher daytime demand, reaching self-consumption near 50%. Offices, limited by shorter operating hours, exhibited the lowest values (5–30%), confirming that operational flexibility is more influential than load magnitude in determining storage value.
- Under the flat tariff scenario, the optimizer favored conservative configurations focused on direct self-consumption, as the low export remuneration (0.066 €/kWh) discouraged oversizing. Residential, retail, and office cases achieved self-consumption of 40.4%, 40.1%, and 5.5%, respectively, with payback periods of 6–7 years. The dual-zone ToU structure (0.130/0.209 €/kWh) introduced temporal differentiation that promoted more active battery operation. Self-consumption increased to 58.2% for residential and 50.5% for retail buildings, while offices reached 25.7%. Payback periods ranged from 6.2 to 7.9 years, indicating modest but consistent economic improvement compared to the flat tariff. Under RTP, hourly price variation between 0.04 and 0.55 €/kWh encouraged the largest storage capacities (up to 18 kWh in retail), though self-consumption gains remained limited. Residential, retail, and office buildings reached 59.9%, 53.6%, and 29.9%, respectively, with paybacks of 6.6–8.1 years. The results show that dynamic tariffs drive flexibility-oriented operation but do not necessarily enhance energy autonomy.
- Across all scenarios, payback periods remain within a narrow range (6–8 years), as the optimizer adapts PV and battery capacities to maintain economic feasibility under each tariff. Larger storage systems under ToU and RTP offset higher investment costs through increased flexibility gains, while smaller, conservative systems emerge under flat pricing. This adaptive sizing behavior explains the stability of paybacks despite significant variations in system configuration and operation.
- The sensitivity analyses reveal that tariff design directly shapes both system sizing and profitability. PV capacity primarily responds to feed-in remuneration, while storage depends on import prices and price volatility. As volatility decreases, battery capacity and economic returns decline, whereas PV sizing remains almost unchanged. Residential systems are largely unaffected by volatility, retail buildings benefit from moderate variability, and office buildings require strong price signals to justify storage investment.
- Overall, moderate temporal differentiation, such as refined ToU tariffs aligned with typical demand profiles, appears to offer the most balanced outcome. It enhances system profitability and operational flexibility without the complexity of full RTP, while future improvements are expected to depend mainly on lower battery costs and better-aligned self-consumption incentives.

This work contributes to the growing body of knowledge on renewable energy integration in buildings, offering a replicable methodology for maximizing economic returns and promoting sustainable energy transitions. The findings provide practical insights for Greek policy, supporting the adoption of dynamic ToU tariffs alongside targeted measures to reduce battery costs. More broadly, the methodology is adaptable to other national contexts by adjusting tariff structures and regulatory provisions.

Future research could explore the optimization of PVB systems within the context of energy communities, which represent a promising evolution from single-building configurations. Energy communities enable shared energy production, storage, and consumption among multiple buildings, creating opportunities for economies of scale, enhanced grid interaction, and improved energy self-sufficiency. Investigating how the optimal system design—particularly in terms of PV and battery sizing—changes when energy demands and generation are aggregated across multiple buildings is a key direction for future work. In addition, future research will integrate detailed battery degradation models that explicitly consider the combined effects of calendar and cycle lifetimes, as well as the associated mid-life replacement costs, thereby improving the accuracy of long-term techno-economic assessments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petros Iliadis: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nikolaos Ziozas:** Writing – original draft,

Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Dimitra Gonidaki**: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Angeliki Kitsopoulou**: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Evangelos Bellos**: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Renos Rotas**: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Nikolaos Nikolopoulos**: Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Elias Kosmatopoulos**: Writing – original draft, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Nomenclature

n	Bus index
t	Snapshot
l	Branch
s	Generator/storage
\bar{g}	Nominal capacity of extendable generator, kW
\bar{h}	Nominal capacity of extendable storage, kWh
$g_{n,s,t}$	Dispatch of the generator, s
$h_{n,s,t}$	Dispatch of storage, h
r	Discount rate, %
n_y	Asset lifetime, years

Abbreviations

ACH	Air Changes per Hour
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DUoS	Distribution Use-of-System
EER	Energy Efficiency Ratio
EU	European Union
FIT	Feed-in-Tariff
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
NPV	Net Present Value
NEM	Net Metering
NEB	Net Billing
pu	per unit
PV	Photovoltaic
PVB	Photovoltaic-Battery
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RTP	Real-Time Pricing
SCOP	Seasonal Coefficient of Performance
ToU	Time-of-Use
TUoS	Transmission Use-of-System
VAT	Value-Added Tax

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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